

Feeding behavior of three *Nephotettix* species on selected rice and graminaceous weeds

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Most studies on green leafhoppers (GLH) involve *Nephotettix virescens*, because it occurs abundantly in many Asian rice-growing countries and because it transmits rice tungro viruses (RTV) more efficiently than other *Nephotettix* species. However, in recent surveys in RTV-infected ricefields in Palawan, Negros Occidental, Nueva Ecija, and Isabela Provinces of the Philippines, *N. nigropictus* comprised 41% and *N. malayanus* 10% of the *Nephotettix* populations. Higher populations of these two species can aggravate RTV incidence and

cumulative populations can worsen RTV outbreaks. Gramineaceous weeds *Leersia hexandra* and *Echinochloa glabrescens* are alternate hosts of these *Nephotettix* species and of RTV.

RTV transmission is linked to insect ability to feed in the phloem of the host plant. We examined the feeding behavior of the three GLH species on GLH-resistant rice varieties Pankhari 203 and IR29 and susceptible TN1, on resistant wild rice *Oryza officinalis* (IRRI acc. # 100896), and on *L. hexandra* and *E. glabrescens* weeds.

Feeding response of 2-d-old GLH females on 30-d-old plants were monitored for 3 h with an electronic recorder. Each plant type was tested seven times for each GLH species, using fresh insects and fresh plants. A bromocresol-green-treated filter paper disk placed below each feeding insect

collected its honeydew. The disk turned blue when the insect fed in the phloem and dull-white when it fed in the xylem.

Feeding response on test plants (probing, salivation, xylem drinking, and phloem ingestion) was the same for the three GLH species (see figure). Durations of each feeding event differed for different GLH species and for different plants. In general, the insects probed more frequently, salivated longer, did more xylem drinking, but did less phloem ingestion on resistant rices and on the wild rice than on susceptible hosts (TN1 for *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* and *L. hexandra* for *N. malayanus*). Blue color reaction of the honeydew on the treated filter paper also confirmed phloem feeding.

The ability of the GLH species to ingest phloem sap from resistant rices and graminaceous weeds renders GLH-resistant rices vulnerable to transmission of phloem-specific tungro viruses. It also implies that RTV can be transferred from weeds to rice and back again. □

Waveforms recorded with an electronic monitoring device during probing by *N. virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *N. malayanus* on resistant Pankhari 203 and IR29 and susceptible TN1 rice plants, wild rice *O. officinalis*, and graminaceous weeds *L. hexandra* and *E. glabrescens*, IIRI, 1989. Charts are to be read from right to left.

Effect of neem oil on courtship signals and mating behavior of brown planthopper (BPH) females

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We noticed a decrease in the buildup of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* population on neem-treated rice plants. We examined whether courtship signals and mating behavior of BPH females were adversely affected by neem oil. Before mating, planthoppers emit signals which are recognized by both sexes.

Fifth-instar BPH nymphs were caged on 30-d-old TN1 rice plants. Females were isolated 3 h after emergence and subjected to -40°C for 2 min. Neem oil was topically applied on their dorsum at 1, 2.5, or $5\ \mu\text{g}/\text{female}$. Control females were treated with $0.1\ \mu\text{l}$ acetone. The females were